

8T – Wave Functions and Spin

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T using the primordial coupling constants series it in the first two forms, i.e. net curvature and spin, it is possible to validate the idea of symmetrical and anti-symmetrical wave functions as presented in the formalism of Quantum mechanics. It is also validate the idea of indistinguishable particles, and the assumption that the second form is validate representation of spin, that is by discrete jumps in value, and thus in energy, which is similar to the structure of the primordial function as presented in the thesis. The theme of the paper is twofold, first deriving the common insights about nature, which intersect with what is known already to be true, using insights of Quantum mechanics. The second is shading new light using variational curvature on why it has to be true, using simpler and more coherent mathematical formalism than the one used in Quantum mechanics.

Introduction

The second main equation of the 8T was derived back in March and is describing the infinite series of coupling magnitudes. The Bosons are discrete amount of Quanta, which is prime amount of net curvature causing matter to cluster. The invariant three proven to be the Electron, which is isomorphic to the Boson of the Weak interaction.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

The second form of the primorial is locating each prime on the prime critical strip. This construction leading to a new form of the original equation, which assumed to be describing the trait of spin. We can solidify that claim using the fact in Quantum mechanics, spin of systems can only change in discrete amounts, that is a positive indication as there is one critical strip in which the Bosons are arising from.

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

That is the first point of intersection with Quantum mechanics. The second point of intersection, is the following. In the paper, "Net Versus Spin", page 140 in the 8T thesis, author argued that the state of the system depends upon the number of elements on the prime critical line, if it is even, the system will behave like a wave, if odd like a Fermion, or particle like. Same argument arisen without the author correlating the arguments at the time, in QM. In particular, symmetrical wave functions versus anti-symmetrical wave functions. Odd numbers obey the Fermi statistics, and Even numbers obey the Bose statistics, which is exactly what the primorial is indicating and the same formalism used to describe the Bosons which act like Fermions, or the Particle wave duality. The author would like to dive deeper into the subject of identical particles and symmetrical versus anti-symmetrical wave functions which serve as a significant part in QM. Suppose a given set of Bosons of a given coupling:

$$K = \{\gamma_1 \dots \gamma_n\}$$

Since all the Bosons are isomorphic to a unique prime there index can change without any difference, i.e. it is impossible to distinguish between two photons.

$$K \rightarrow N_{V=2}$$

$$\forall \gamma_n \in K$$

The same apply to each Boson of each coupling in the series. The notion of equivalence can be solidified using the idea of class. All Bosons belong to the class of curvature on the manifold, page 176 in the thesis, and thus it is possible to expend the idea of indistinguishable to classes of Bosons. As an example, consider the arrow:

$$T: (K \rightarrow N_{V=2}) \rightarrow K_2$$

Alternatively, more generally:

$$T: (K \rightarrow N_{V=Z}) \rightarrow K_Z$$

Since all Bosons belong to the same class, we can create an higher class, summing the distinct classes of Bosons;

$$\mathcal{T} = \{K_1 \dots K_Z\}$$

$$K_1 \equiv K_2 \dots \equiv K_Z$$

The last point of intersection is the nature of Bosons versus the nature of Fermions, excluding the complication arises from the duality of the Electron and W Boson. Since Bosons has only one sign, that is they are net amount (assumed positive, although it makes no difference and considered negative) they are described under one sign in the thesis. And thus, if the Boson is interchanged it makes no difference to sign of the wave function.

Consider the set of signs to the class of Bosons to be a subset of discrete amount:

$$\mathfrak{X}_B \subset \mathcal{T}$$

$$\mathfrak{X}_B = \{+\}$$

While Fermions are vanishing curvature spikes, the set of elements for class for Fermions, excluding the Electron, would then be:

$$\mathcal{F} = \{\delta g_1, \delta g_2\}$$

Consider the set of signs to the class of Fermions to be a subset of discrete amount:

$$\mathfrak{X}_F \subset \mathcal{F}$$

$$\mathfrak{X}_F = \{+, -\}$$

Thus the interchange of Bosons does not change the sign of the wave function, while the interchange of Fermions does changes the sign of the wave function. The immediate result is that Bosons can be propagated as wave to long-range distances, while Fermions cannot. That is similar to stating that the Fermions will accelerate toward one another. Another way to explain it is to state that the opposite curvature ripples cancel each other out, yielding an higher level entity which has no curvature manifestation, what we call matter. A threefold combination must match another threefold combination to eliminate the curvature ripples, in agreement with stationary manifold. The exclusion of the Electron is due to the fact that it is isomorphic to the Boson of the weak interaction, which imposes a complication as it can theoretically belonged to either Fermions or Bosons.

Summing up in three points. First point, the wave function of systems should be classified according to certain criteria. The first is the Bosonic or Fermionic classes, the second is the number of elements in the class.

Second point, Fermion class must contain an even number of elements, Bosonic class can contain any number of element, if the number is even, the statistic obey the Bose rules, if it is odd than Fermi rules.

Third, the number of elements dictates the spin summation using the prime critical line. The spin summation determines the behavior of the system, which can be either a smooth wave or particle like. The symmetry of wave function is due to subset of signs to each of the two distinct classes. The number of elements also dictating the Quanta's of energy in the system.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad's Theory